

QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF POTABLE WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS SUPPLIED BY KHULNA WASA, BANGLADESH

Md. Hafijur Rahman Sabbir*¹, Md. Rashedul Islam² and Md. Asif All Azad³

¹ Undergraduate student, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh, e-mail: sabbir.hafijur.rahman@gmail.com

² Undergraduate student, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh, e-mail: md.rashedulislam.kuet@gmail.com

³ Undergraduate student, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh, e-mail: asif.che.kuet@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

The residents of Khulna City have been struggling with the scarcity of potable water for many years. KWASA (Khulna Water Supply and Sewerage Authority) provides potable water to the dwellers of Khulna City by utilizing its groundwater distribution network. This study collected KWASA-supplied water samples from 17 locations across Khulna City. It was found that in some areas, the supplied water is used for both household cleaning and drinking purposes, while in the rest of the areas, it is merely used for domestic non-drinking purposes. Therefore, assessment of the significant water quality parameters for potable water is essential in this region. In this study, a thorough evaluation was performed to evaluate water quality indicators, such as Dissolved Oxygen (DO), pH, conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), salt content, hardness, and turbidity. The pH values obtained from the samples ranged from 7.41 to 6.01, which falls within the recommended pH range of 6.5 to 8.5 by the World Health Organization (WHO) and Bangladesh Standards (BDS). The study revealed that total hardness varied between 132 mg/L and 1050 mg/L. Most of these values didn't follow the BDS standard of 200–500 mg/L. The DO levels ranged from 0.6 to 2.8 mg/L, which is significantly below the 6 mg/L BDS norm for DO. This investigation also found that TDS values ranged from 176 mg/L to 1400 mg/L. Few TDS concentration values exceed BDS and WHO standards limit of 1000 mg/L. Moreover, the recorded turbidity readings ranged from 0.46 NTU to 5.91 NTU. Most of the turbidity readings complied with the limit set by the WHO and the BDS, which is 5 NTU. The conductivity was between 263 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 2100 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Some of the samples exceeded the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) permitted maximum conductivity value of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The other water quality parameters also deviated considerably from the WHO and BDS recommended standard values which are analyzed in this study.

Keywords: KWASA; potable water; water quality; BDS; WHO

1. Introduction

Drinking water is one of the most essential components of the physical environment [1]. The quality of drinking water is closely linked to various aspects of human existence, well-being, economic progress, food availability, alleviation of poverty, and the maintenance of sustainable natural systems [2]. Drinking water contamination is one of the leading environmental causes of illness and early mortality in underdeveloped countries, making it one of our most significant existential issues [3]. It has been estimated that around 80% of illnesses and more than one-third of fatalities in developing nations can be linked to the drinking of contaminated water. Additionally, on average, individuals in these regions sacrifice approximately one-tenth of their productive time due to diseases caused by water [4]. Due to rural migration and economic expansion, drinking water quality in Bangladesh is at high risk, especially in urban areas like Khulna [5], [6].

In Bangladesh, groundwater serves as the primary source for drinking and various purposes. A variety of water quality issues affect Bangladesh's groundwater systems in the south-western coastal zone [7], [8]. Still, the south-western coastal region of the nation is encountering significant obstacles to fulfilling the increasing need for freshwater, primarily due to the restricted availability of both groundwater and surface water sources. These sources are adversely impacted by salt and other water quality issues [9]. With the exception of certain areas, the water in Khulna is unsuitable for drinking; the potability of groundwater exhibits geographical variation with respect to depth, while shallow water is deemed entirely unsuitable for human consumption [10]. A study was conducted to evaluate the potable water quality of the groundwater in Khulna City, Bangladesh, utilizing the water

quality index (WQI). Water was collected for the study from 59 tube wells in Khulna City prior to the monsoon. The total hardness, pH, EC, DO, TDS, Cl^- , and NO_3^- of water samples were determined. The study found that the groundwater quality in most areas of Khulna City was safe and suitable for drinking, except for elevated electric conductivity (EC) and Cl^- content in some areas, possibly due to the proximity to the Bay of Bengal [11]. In another investigation, researchers analyzed the physicochemical properties of ground and surface water samples from all over Khulna City Corporation of Bangladesh and concluded that the water supply meets both BDS and WHO standards for potable use with the exception of two samples with abnormally high turbidity and Cl^- content. According to the article, the quality of the water supply in the Nirala, Sonadanga, Rupsha, and Hadispark areas of Khulna has been found to be below the acceptable standards for drinkable water [12].

Khulna faces acute potable water issues, mainly due to high saline levels in water sources. The establishment of the Khulna Water Supply and Sewerage Authority (KWASA) in 2008 marked a significant step towards addressing the drinking water crisis. This autonomous organization was created with the primary objective of ensuring sufficient access to safe drinking water and effective sewerage systems for the residents of Khulna. The present water provision rendered by KWASA to the entirety of the region amounts to 110 million liters per day, which is facilitated by a network of pipelines [13]. Another study found that over 90% of consumers drink shallow and deep tube well water instead of pipe water. Most individuals are not satisfied with the quality and amount of their daily water [14]. A diverse range of physical, chemical, and biological alterations may occur as water traverses a network system of distribution pipelines [15]. The objective of the study is to analyze several essential properties of drinking water and to evaluate the findings with respect to acceptable national and international specifications. As contaminated water can pose a health concern to Khulna residents, the current analysis was done to assess essential water quality characteristics of the KWASA's supply water. The criteria under evaluation include DO, TDS, pH, turbidity, hardness, and EC.

2. Materials and Methods

Fig. 1 presents a flowchart showing the sequence of operations that were performed in this study.

Fig. 1: Flow chart of the experimental procedure

A preliminary field reconnaissance study was undertaken in order to identify suitable sample locations that would efficiently record the whole of KWASA's distribution network. Subsequently, samples were obtained from specified locations using newly sterilized one-liter plastic bottles, which were meticulously cleansed by repeated washing with the water intended for sampling purposes. The samples were primarily obtained from the tube wells and taps located within the residents' households, to which KWASA supplies. People utilize the supplied water for everyday necessities and consumption, including drinking. Prior to collecting samples from production tube wells and water taps, an adequate volume of water was taken out in order to ensure that the sample accurately represents the composition of the original supplied water. Following that, the sampling bottles were filled to their maximum capacity and immediately sealed in order to prevent any contact with atmospheric air. The samples were appropriately labeled with their respective identification numbers, sources, locations, and dates of collection. The samples were collected and preserved in accordance with standard protocols and procedures. Testing and analysis were subsequently conducted in the laboratory. The water quality parameters were assessed by comparing the test results with the established standards set by the BDS and the WHO guidelines for drinking water quality.

2.1 Description of the Study Area

According to the KWASA, the covered service area is estimated to be 45.60 square kilometers. The current population residing within the specified region is estimated to be 1.50 million individuals in the Khulna City Corporation (KCC). Furthermore, it is estimated that the population being supplied amounts to around 1.10 million individuals. KWASA is presently engaged in the operation of a combined number of 9,000 hand tube wells and

41 production tube wells. The current total of household connections amounts to 40,368 [13]. Table 1 and Figure 2 show the sampling location of this study.

Table 1: Locations of sampling

Sample No.	Locations	Sample No.	Locations
Sample 1	122 M A Bari Street, Khulna 9208	Sample 10	Voirob Stand Road, Khulna
Sample 2	Farukia Mosque Cross Road, Boyra	Sample 11	Goalkhali Bus Stand
Sample 3	Khulna 250 Bed General Hospital, Khulna	Sample 12	Muzgunni Kazi Para, Khulna
Sample 4	East Bania Khamar, Khulna	Sample 13	Boikali Bazar, Khulna
Sample 5	Nirala Residential Area	Sample 14	Tutpara, Khulna
Sample 6	Basupara main road, Khulna	Sample 15	Shaikh Para Staff Quarter, Khulna
Sample 7	175 Bagmara Main Road, Khulna 9100	Sample 16	Alom nogor, Khalishpur
Sample 8	Rupsha Strand Road, Khulna 9100	Sample 17	Khalishpur Housing State
Sample 9	32 Ahsan Ahmed Road, Khulna 9100		

Fig. 2: Study area and sample collection locations

3. Results and Discussions

The water samples were analyzed to determine the values for pH, turbidity, hardness, dissolved oxygen (DO), total dissolved solids (TDS), and conductivity following standard methods. The overview of the sample test result is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of sample test result

Water quality parameters	DO (mg/L)	pH	EC (μS/cm)	TDS (mg/L)	Salt (%)	Hardness (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)
Sample No							
01	1.1	6.94	2100	1400	0.12	1050	0.98
02	0.8	7.2	941	627	0.05	470	5.91
03	2.8	6.5	269	179	0.02	134	2.04
04	1.0	6.24	624	421	0.04	331	1.13
05	0.8	6.27	623	416	0.04	311	2.91
06	0.9	6.50	1460	973	0.08	728	0.68
07	1.1	6.08	268	179	0.02	134	2.90
08	0.9	6.78	771	513	0.04	385	1.13
09	0.9	7.25	300	200	0.02	150	0.36
10	0.8	6.90	1260	840	0.07	630	2.47
11	1.0	7.12	287	191	0.02	143	3.83
12	0.6	6.95	308	205	0.02	154	2.66
13	0.9	6.73	1649	1098	0.09	823	0.89
14	1.2	6.03	285	190	0.02	142	2.73
15	0.6	7.41	276	184	0.02	138	0.46
16	1.2	6.01	263	176	0.01	132	1.72
17	0.9	6.03	273	182	0.02	136	3.22

The evaluation of the different water quality parameter values was carried out by a comparison of the test results with the established guidelines for drinking water quality provided by the WHO and the BDS. Table 3 presents a comparison between the test results of the KWASA water samples and these established standards.

Table 3: Comparison of the different water quality parameters with WHO and BDS standards [17, 18]

Water quality parameters	Determination methods/ Apparatus	Maximum value	Minimum Value	Water quality standards of the WHO and BDS		Percentage of samples not following WHO and BDS standards	
				WHO	BDS	WHO	BDS
DO (mg/L)	Multimeter	2.8	0.6	6	-	-	100
pH	Digital pH meter	7.41	6.01	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	35.3	35.3
Conductivity (μS/cm)	Multimeter	2100	263	1200	-	23.53	-
TDS (mg/L)	Titrimetric analysis	1400	176	1000	1000	11.76	11.76
Hardness (mg/L)	Titrimetric Analysis	1050	132	500	200-500	23.53	76.47
Turbidity (NTU)	Turbidity meter	5.91	0.46	5	10	5.58	0

pH: The pH value counts as a significant indicator, and maintaining a regulated pH value is crucial in water supplies, sewage treatment, and chemical process facilities. Consuming water with an excessively low or high pH

level might pose harmful effects on health. Excessive acidity in water has the potential to induce damage to teeth, and a highly alkaline state of water may lead to gastrointestinal issues [16]. The WHO and the BDS have established a prescribed pH range of 6.5 to 8.5 for drinking water. The pH values measured during this study exhibited a range from 6.01 to 7.41. Among the 17 samples analyzed, it was observed that 35.3% of the samples were out of the acceptable range of pH for drinking water. The maximum value of pH was found in sample 15, and the minimum value was observed in sample 16.

Fig. 3: pH of different samples

DO: The dissolved oxygen (DO) is a vital indicator in the evaluation of water quality. It is an important parameter that affects the survival of aquatic organisms. The quality of drinking water is closely related with the amounts of DO. A decrease in DO levels is indicative of the existence of pollutants and microbiological contamination [17]. In this investigation, all of the samples exhibited concentrations which are below the WHO-recommended threshold of 6 mg/L. The highest recorded DO concentration was 2.8 mg/L, and the lowest obtained value was 0.6 mg/L. This findings suggest the water has significant presence of aquatic contamination.

Fig. 4: DO of different samples

Hardness: The presence of excessive hardness in water can enhance the production of scale in pipes and appliances. It can also cause irritation of the skin, cardiovascular disease and hair damage [18]. The hardness among the samples exhibited a range from 132 mg/L to 1050 mg/L. The WHO has established a permitted limit of 500 mg/L for hardness in drinking water, while the BDS standard is from 200 to 500 mg/L. 23.53% of the samples analyzed in this study did not comply with the WHO standard. In contrast, it was observed that 76.47% of the samples did not adhere to the BDS limit for hardness in drinking water. The high hardness of KWASA water can be attributed to the presence of dissolved calcium and magnesium salts. Sample 1 had the highest recorded hardness value, while sample 16 displayed the lowest measured reading.

Fig. 5: Hardness of different samples

Total dissolved solids (TDS): The WHO and the BDS have set the maximum acceptable TDS value in drinking water at 1000 mg/L. Among the 17 samples, a wide range of values starting from 176 mg/L to 1400 mg/L were found. Sample 1 had the highest TDS content, and the lowest value was present in sample 16. The result shows that 11.76% of the samples did not align with the permitted limit of TDS for drinking water as set by the WHO and the BDS. Excessive TDS may cause unpleasant taste and odor in drinking water [19]

Fig. 6: TDS of different samples

Turbidity: Turbidity is an index for evaluating the transparency of water. The WHO has set a permitted maximum value of 5 Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU) in drinking water. The BDS limit of turbidity for drinking water is up to 10 NTU. Among the 17 samples the test values were ranged between 0.46 to 5.91 NTU. All of the samples complied with the WHO standard. Only sample 2 was found to exceed the acceptable range according to the BDS specifications. Turbidity in drinking water is associated with gastrointestinal illness [20]

Fig. 7: Turbidity of different samples

Electrical Conductivity (EC): Conductivity refers to the quantitative assessment of water's capacity to facilitate the flow of electric current. Elevated conductivity levels in water could act as an indicator of the existence of dissolved solids and other inorganic compounds. These substances have the potential to impact sensory attributes, such as taste and odor, as well as the overall quality of potable water. Among the samples 23.53% of them exceeded the WHO permissible limit of conductivity. According to the EPA, it is recommended that the conductivity of drinking water should be maintained at a level below 1,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ [21]. The study observed a variety of conductivity values, ranging from 263 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 2100 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, among the collected samples. The sample with the highest conductivity identified was sample 1, whereas sample 16 had the lowest conductivity.

Fig. 8: Conductivity of different samples

4. Conclusion

After detailed scrutiny of the results obtained from this study, it becomes evident that there are substantial variances in the water quality parameters supplied by KWASA across the Khulna region. The majority of the samples fell within the acceptable pH range. However, a few samples had acidic trends. The findings revealed a significant drop in DO levels across all samples, suggesting compromised drinking water quality. The majority of the samples exhibited turbidity levels within the acceptable range for drinking water, suggesting that the water is clear. The TDS levels in the majority of the samples appeared to be adequate. Several of the samples surpassed the acceptable amount of hardness. The increased hardness of water can be attributed to the existence of dissolved salts of calcium and magnesium. Four of the samples tested exceeded the conductivity level set by the EPA. The study revealed limited use of the supplied water for drinking purposes, such as sample 16, where the water is consumed for both drinking and other activities. The water quality test results obtained from the samples of KWASA's distribution system indicate that the water quality is unsatisfactory across many locations. It is suggested that the authority in charge implements a routine monitoring initiative in order to proactively mitigate the risk of water pollution throughout its distribution network. Periodic identification of geological formations and regular repair of pipelines are essential responsibilities in this respect. Furthermore, authorities must assess the efficacy of various water treatment methods in order to enhance the appropriateness of it.

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References

- [1] A. A. Lipu and K. M. M. Ekram, "Assessing the Spatial Variations of Supplied Drinking Water Quality of Khulna WASA, Bangladesh".
- [2] U. ESCAP, *Water security & the global water agenda: A UN-water analytical brief*. United Nations University (UNU), 2013.
- [3] R. Connor *et al.*, *The United Nations World Water Development Report 2017. Wastewater: The Untapped Resource*. 2017.
- [4] "Agenda 21, Chapter 18: Protection of the Quality and Supply of Freshwater Resources".
- [5] "Assessment of supply water quality in the Chittagong city of Bangladesh," vol. 4, no. 3, 2009.

- [6] K. Fahmida, H. R. Lemon, S. Islam, and A. Kader, "Assessment of Supplied Water Quality of Khulna WASA of Bangladesh," 2013.
- [7] S. Adhikary, M. Elahi, and A. M. Hossain, "Assessment of Shallow Groundwater Quality from Six Wards of Khulna City Corporation, Bangladesh," *International Journal of Applied Sciences and Engineering Research*, vol. 1, pp. 488–498, Jul. 2012, doi: 10.6088/ijaser.0020101050.
- [8] A. Henderson, L. Roberts, J. Bogan, C. H. Rubin, and J. C. Semenza, "Water distribution system and diarrheal disease transmission: a case study in Uzbekistan.," *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 941–946, Dec. 1998, doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.1998.59.941.
- [9] md elahi and S. Adhikary, *Assessment of Shallow Groundwater Quality from Six Wards of Khulna City Corporation, Bangladesh*. 2012.
- [10] M. B. Alam, C. R. K. Rocky, N. S. Tarakki, A. Al Aftab, and C. Quamruzzaman, "Groundwater and Surface Water Quality Assessment for Irrigation and Drinking Purposes of Khulna District, South-Western, Bangladesh.," 2015.
- [11] A. Mahmud, S. Sikder, and J. C. Joardar, "Assessment of groundwater quality in Khulna city of Bangladesh in terms of water quality index for drinking purpose," *Appl Water Sci*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 226, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13201-020-01314-z.
- [12] S. Nasrin, S. K. Saha, and M. M. S. Rahman, "ASSESSMENT OF SUPPLY WATER QUALITY OF KHULNA CITY CORPORATION, KHULNA, BANGLADESH," *Khulna Univ. Stud.*, pp. 13–19, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.53808/KUS.2005.6.1and2.0341-L.
- [13] "Khulna Water Supply and Sewerage Authority." Accessed: Nov. 07, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kwasa.org.bd/kwasa/en/home.aspx>
- [14] M. N. Uddin, M. M. Bahar, M. A. Islam, and A. Y. A. Harun, "AN EVALUATION OF WATER SUPPLY SCENARIO IN KHULNA CITY CORPORATION AREA," *Khulna Univ. Stud.*, pp. 33–36, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.53808/KUS.2006.7.1.0522-L.
- [15] Z. Michael Lahlou, "Water Quality in Distribution Systems," in *Water Encyclopedia*, 1st ed., J. H. Lehr and J. Keeley, Eds., Wiley, 2004, pp. 204–207. doi: 10.1002/047147844X.mw1822.
- [16] T. H. Hansen *et al.*, "The effect of drinking water pH on the human gut microbiota and glucose regulation: results of a randomized controlled cross-over intervention," *Sci Rep*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 16626, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-34761-5.
- [17] O. Bozorg-Haddad, M. Delpasand, and H. A. Loáiciga, "Water quality, hygiene, and health," in *Economical, Political, and Social Issues in Water Resources*, Elsevier, 2021, pp. 217–257. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-323-90567-1.00008-5.
- [18] R. Kumar, "Potential Health Impacts of Hard Water: A Review of Literature," *IJRASET*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 3442–3444, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.22214/ijraset.2024.60622.
- [19] M. Rafiqul Islam, "A Study on the TDS Level of Drinking Mineral Water in Bangladesh," *AJAC*, vol. 4, no. 5, p. 164, 2016, doi: 10.11648/j.ajac.20160405.11.
- [20] J. Schwartz and R. Levin, "Drinking Water Turbidity and Health," *Epidemiology*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 86–90, 1999.
- [21] "5.9 Conductivity | Monitoring & Assessment | US EPA." Accessed: Nov. 10, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://archive.epa.gov/water/archive/web/html/vms59.html>